

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

HOCHSCHULE MAINZ
UNIVERSITY OF
APPLIED SCIENCES

Geodata in Linked Open Data and Wikidata in Practice

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Timo Homburg (Hochschule Mainz University of Applied Sciences)

Open Science Festival 2024 | Mainz | 17.09.2024

Hi :-)

Who we are?

Über uns Projekte **Team** News Kontakt DE / EN

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Aktiv seit 2015

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Funktionen	Wissenschaftlicher Mitarbeiter
Forschung	Datenbanken GIS Semantisches Web Künstliche Intelligenz und Semantic Web Computerlinguistik Geospatial Semantic Web Standardisierung
Gutachterfunktionen	International Conference on Advances in Semantic Processing Heritage Science Journal ISPRS International Journal for Geoinformation Computers Journal MDPI MDPI Information Digital Scholarship in the Humanities Journal DH2018, DH2019, DH2020 DHd2019
Mitgliedschaften	Open Geospatial Consortium Chaos Computer Club

Timo Homburg i3mainz, CC BY SA 4.0

Forschung Museen Über uns Aktuelles Presse

Start > Über uns > Team > Florian Thiery, M.Sc.

Florian Thiery, M.Sc.

Research Software Engineer (NFDI4Objects)

NFDI4Objects
Community Cluster
Research Software
Engineering (RSE)

NFDI4Objects
Community Cluster
Semantic Modelling
& Linked Open Data

Forschungsprofil

- Research Software Engineering
- Semantische Modellierung (semantic modelling)
- Linked Open Data / Wikidata
- Vagheiten und Unsicherheiten (Fuzziness and Wobbliness)
- Relative Chronologie

KONTAKT

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 Kontakt

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 Teilen

 Link kopieren

 Artikel drucken

Werdegang

Akademischer Werdegang

- 2013: Master-Thesis, [Semantic Web und Linked Data: Generierung von Interoperabilität in archäologischen Fachdaten am Beispiel römischer Topferstempel](#). Betreuer: Prof. Dr. phil. Kai-Christian Bruhn, Partner: i3mainz and RGZM, Note: 1.0 (sehr gut)
- 2011-2013: Studium der Geoinformatik und Vermessung an der Fachhochschule Mainz, Abschluss: Master of Science, Note 1.5 (sehr gut)
- 2011: Bachelor-Thesis: [Eignung aktueller Industriekameras für modulare Digitalkameratachymeter](#). Betreuer: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Martin Schlüter, Partner: i3mainz, Note: 1.7 (gut)
- 2007-2011: Studium der Geoinformatik und Vermessung an der Fachhochschule Mainz, Abschluss: Bachelor of Science, Note: 2.3 (gut)

Who we are?

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We are part of the Research Squirrel Engineers Network

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WIKIDATA

R D F

... the developer of the SPARQL Unicorn

QGIS

GitHub

Who are you?

- Name
- Affiliation
- experience with LOD?
- why are you here?
- any wishes?

Introduction

Graphs in Archaeology

FAIRification is the basis of Open Data!

FINDABLE

ACCESSIBLE

INTEROPERABLE

REUSABLE

The Semantic Web in Digital Humanities

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

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The Semantic Web ...

... extends the web to make data easier to exchange between computers and easier for them to use. Standards for publishing and using machine-readable data (especially RDF) are used to realise this.

The Semantic Web ...

Paul Clarke, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

... isn't just about putting data on the web. It is about making links, so that a person or machine can explore the web of data. With linked data, when you have some of it, you can find other, related, data.

from <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Linked Open Data leads to FAIR data!

local (offline)

online

online & open

part of LOD

FAIRification is a goal of NFDI4Objects

A research data infrastructure a research data infrastructure
for the material legacy of approx. 2.6 million years of human history

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

FAIRification can only succeed in co-operation with the consortia from the humanities/cultural sciences, geosciences and life sciences

Vanessa Liebler / NFDI4Objects, CC BY-SA 4.0

The Humanities MoU-Group

Geistes- und kulturwissenschaftliche Konsortien
in der NFDI

Be part of NFDI4Objects!

**Community Cluster:
Semantic Modelling & LOD**

Community Cluster

TWG

Linked Open Data

Classes, Instances and Properties

David Rasp, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Classes, Instances and Properties

Fotograv. - Generalstabens Litografiska Anstalt Stockholm, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons

Linked Data is based on RDF

image via ontotext.com

Linked Data

Linked Data Principles

5 Star Data

via <https://5stardata.info/> and <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Linked Data Principles

Linked Data

The Semantic Web isn't just about putting data on the web. It is about making links, so that a person or machine can explore the web of data. With linked data, when you have some of it, you can find other, related, data.

Like the web of hypertext, the web of data is constructed with documents on the web. However, unlike the web of hypertext, where links are relationships anchors in hypertext documents written in HTML, for data they links between arbitrary things described by RDF,. The URIs identify any kind of object or concept. But for HTML or RDF, the same expectations apply to make the web grow:

1. Use URIs as names for things
2. Use HTTP URIs so that people can look up those names.
3. When someone looks up a URI, provide useful information, using the standards (RDF*, SPARQL)
4. Include links to other URIs so that they can discover more things.

from <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Linked Open Data Cloud

2007

2008

2009

2010

2011

2017

2018

2019

2020

2023

Classes vs. Features vs. Feature Collections

GeoSPARQL Query Language

An extension of SPARQL to map relations between geometries

SPARQL Query Language

SPARQL Query Language

from <https://wordlift.io/blog/en/entity/sparql/>

Linked Open Data in Action

(Examples from the Humanities ...)

nomisma.org

nomisma.org Browse IDs Research Tools APIs Documentation Ontology SPARQL Datasets

Laodicea ad Mare (Mint, Concept)

Canonical URI: http://nomisma.org/id/laodiceia_ad_mare

Labels
Preferred Label: Laodicea ad Mare (en), Λαττακίῶν (fr), Λατᾶκια (es), Laodicea (it), Λατᾶκια (de), Λαττακία (el) Additional labels ▶
Alternate Label: Laodiceia pros Mare (en)

Definitions
en The mint at the ancient site of Laodicea in Syria.

Geospatial Data
URI: http://nomisma.org/id/laodiceia_ad_mare#this
Latitude: 35.516967
Longitude: 35.783333
Part Of: http://nomisma.org/id/seleucia_and_pieria#this

Relations
Broader Concept: http://nomisma.org/id/seleucia_and_pieria
Close Match: <http://collection.britishmuseum.org/id/place/x48252>
Close Match: <http://d-nb.info/gnd/4270543-5>
Close Match: <http://dtpedia.org/resource/laotakia>
Close Match: <http://sws.geonames.org/173576/>
Close Match: <http://sws.geonames.org/8445122/>
Close Match: <http://viaf.org/viaf/135413368>
Close Match: <http://vocab.getty.edu/tn/7022280>
Close Match: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q200030>
Close Match: <https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/688290>
Close Match: <https://www.freebase.com/m/01bamp>
Concept Scheme: <http://nomisma.org/id/>

Miscellaneous
Part Of: http://nomisma.org/id/greek_numismatics
Part Of: http://nomisma.org/id/roman_numismatics
Part Of: http://nomisma.org/id/roman_provincial_numismatics

Export

Linked Data: [GitHub](#) [File](#) [RDF/XML](#) [RDF/TTL](#) [JSON-LD](#)
Geographic Data: [KML](#) [GeoJSON](#)

Legend: ■ Mints ■ Hoards ■ Finds

Type	AuthorityID	MintID	DenominationID	Date1	Example
Selected Coins (part 1) 36	Seleucia I Number	Laodicea ad Mare	Tetradrachm	300 BCE - 200 BCE	
Selected Coins (part 1) 27	Seleucia I Number	Laodicea ad Mare	Diachme	300 BCE - 200 BCE	
Selected Coins (part 1) 257	Antiochia I Obol	Laodicea ad Mare	Tetradrachm	201 BCE - 201 BCE	
Selected Coins (part 1) 255	Antiochia I Obol	Laodicea ad Mare	Diachme	201 BCE - 201 BCE	
Selected Coins (part 1) 302	Antiochia I Obol	Laodicea ad Mare	Tetradrachm	270 BCE - 201 BCE	
Selected Coins (part 1) 515	Antiochia I Obol	Laodicea ad Mare	Tetradrachm	201 BCE - 200 BCE	
Selected Coins (part 1) 355	Seleucia II Obolus	Laodicea ad Mare	Tetradrachm	230 BCE - 225 BCE	
Prop. 509		Laodicea ad Mare	Tetradrachm	200 BCE - 200 BCE	

Nomisma | http://nomisma.org/id/laodiceia_ad_mare

kerameikos.org

Kerameikos.org | [Browse](#) | [Research Tools](#) | [Ontology](#) | [APIs](#) | [Documentation](#) | [SPARQL](#) | [Databases](#) |

Objects of this Typology | Quantitative Analysis

Bowl (Shape, Concept)

Canonical URI: <http://kerameikos.org/id/bowl>

Labels

Preferred Label Bowl (en), bol (fr), catola (it), Schüssel (de), λικάνη (el) Additional labels ▶

Definitions

- en The term bowl is used to designate a plain, open shape without handles.
- de Begriff zur Beschreibung einer einfachen, offenen Form ohne Henkel.
- el Ο δίσκος περιλαμβάνει ένα ασύμ, ανοικτό αγγείο χωρίς χερούλι.

Relations

- Exact Match <http://vocab.getty.edu/aid/300203986>
- Exact Match <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q133988>
- Exact Match <https://www.britishmuseum.org/collectors/term/5597>
- Reference <https://zenon.dainet.org/Record/000926820>

Data Provenance ▶

Data Export: [RDF/XML](#) | [TTL](#) | [JSON-LD](#)

Map showing findspots (red circles) and places (blue squares) in the Mediterranean region.

Objects of this Typology ▼

These objects are associated by artist signature or scholarly attribution by analyzing artistic similarities. Only those with images are shown below, but all objects related to the concept are queried for other visualizations and data downloads.

Records 1 to 48 of 310

1 2 3 4 Next ▶ 7 ▶

Kerameikos | <http://kerameikos.org/id/bowl>

Linked Open Samian Ware | Samian Research

LEIZA Linked Open Samian Ware | <https://rgzm.github.io/samian-lod/>

Linked Ogham Data

Linked Ogham Data | <http://ogham.link>

Wikidata & FactGrid

Wikidata

Wikidata ...

What is Wikidata?

- ✦ **A free and open knowledge base and data hub**
→ everybody can add and edit
- ✦ central storage for structured data of **Wikimedia** projects

data in **Wikidata** is:

- ✦ **available** under a free license (CC 0)
- ✦ **multilingual**
- ✦ **accessible** to humans and machines (GUI & API & SPARQL)
- ✦ **exportable** using standard formats (JSON, RDF, XML)
- ✦ **interlinked** to other open data sets on the LOD Cloud

Wikidata and the LOD Cloud

local (offline)

online

online & open

part of LOD

Wikidata in the Linked Open Data Cloud

Linked Data & Wikidata in archaeology

via 10.3390/digital2030019

The screenshot shows the MDPI Digital journal article page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the MDPI logo, links for Journals, Topics, Information, Author Services, Initiatives, and About, and buttons for Sign In / Sign Up and Submit. Below this is a search bar with fields for Title / Keyword, Author / Affiliation / Email, Digital (selected), and All Article Types, along with Search and Advanced buttons. The breadcrumb trail reads: Journals / Digital / Volume 2 / Issue 3 / 10.3390/digital2030019.

The article page features a left sidebar with the journal logo, submission and review buttons, and an Article Menu. The menu includes Academic Editors (Markos Katsianis, Tuna Kalayci, Apostolos Sarris), Subscribe SciFeed, Recommended Articles, Related Info Link, and More by Authors Links. At the bottom of the sidebar, Article Views are 5726 and Citations are 7.

The main content area displays the article title "Practices of Linked Open Data in Archaeology and Their Realisation in Wikidata" by Sophie C. Schmidt^{1,*}, Florian Thiery², and Martina Trognitz³. The authors' affiliations are listed: ¹ Institut für Prähistorische Archäologie and Berlin Graduate School of Ancient Studies, Freie Universität Berlin, 14195 Berlin, Germany; ² Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum, Department of Scientific IT, Digital Platforms and Research Tools, 55116 Mainz, Germany; ³ Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage, Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften, 1010 Vienna, Austria. A note indicates that * is the author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

The article is published in *Digital* 2022, 2(3), 333-364; <https://doi.org/10.3390/digital2030019>. Submission received: 20 April 2022 / Revised: 2 June 2022 / Accepted: 17 June 2022 / Published: 22 June 2022. A note states: (This article belongs to the Special Issue Bridging Digital Approaches and Legacy in Archaeology).

Buttons for Download, Browse Figures, Review Reports, and Versions Notes are available. The abstract states: "In this paper, we introduce Linked Open Data (LOD) in the archaeological domain as a means to connect dispersed data sources and enable cross-querying. The technology behind the design principles and how LOD can be created and published is described to enable less-familiar researchers to understand the presented benefits and drawbacks of LOD. Wikidata is introduced as an open knowledge hub for the creation and dissemination of LOD. Different actors within archaeology have implemented LOD, and we present which challenges have been and are being addressed. A selection of projects showcases how Wikidata is being used by archaeologists to enrich and open their databases to the general public. With this paper, we aim to encourage the creation and re-use of LOD in archaeology, as we believe it offers an improvement on current data publishing practices." The keywords are: linked open data; Wikidata; archaeology.

The right sidebar contains an Altmetric icon, a Share button, a Help button, a Cite button, a Discuss in SciProfiles button, an Endorse button, and a Comment button.

Linked Data in Wikidata: An example

Olaf Tausch, CC BY 3.0, via Wikimedia Commons

<https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q465338>

<https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q249707>

<https://www.wikidata.org/entity/P189>

Grafiken: Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via 10.3390/digital2030019

Linked Data in Wikidata: An example

Grafiken: Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via 10.3390/digital2030019

Wikidata Datamodel

Mtrognitz, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

SPARQL Query: Amphoras in Wikidata

Wikidata Query Service

Examples Help More tools

1 (Input a SPARQL query or choose a query example)

 ? <w.wiki/8Xh>

query.wikidata.org

SPARQL Query: Amphoras in Wikidata

w.wiki/8Xh

Ogham!

R.A.S. Macalister, *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, vol. I (1945) / p.502

CIIC 197. Florian Thiery, CC BY-SA 4.0

Al-qamar, CC BY-SA 3.0, via Wikimedia Commons

The Open Ogham Data Workflow!

Florian Thiery, Timo Homburg, Sophie C. Schmidt und Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

SPARQL Query: Ogham in Wikidata

query.wikidata.org

SPARQL Query: Ogham in Wikidata

```
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?img WHERE {  
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q2016147.  
  OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P625 ?geo. }  
  OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img. }  
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }  
}
```


Wikidata, beyond concepts

Linguistic Linked Open Data in Wikidata

Idea: Collect all words in all languages of the world, dead or alive!

Lexeme: L1122

[Wikidata](#)

Description	Value	Source
Lemma	dog	
Language	English	
Lexical category	noun	
Word stem		
Derived from		
Homographs	dog	

[Edit on query.Wikidata.org](#)

Form	Features
dog	singular
dogs	plural

[Edit on query.Wikidata.org](#)

Sense	Glosses	Sense image
L1122-S1	<p>anjing // mamífero doméstico // domesticated mammal related to the wolf // huisdier dat afstamt van de wolf // mamífero usado como animal de estimação e parente dos lobos // домашнее животное отряда собачьих // zwierzę domowe spokrewnione z wilkiem // adupan</p>	
L1122-S2	tool in engineering	

Linguistic Linked Open Data in Wikidata: Lexeme

- Lexeme with lexical category and language
- A set of grammatical forms
- A set of senses linking to Wikidata concepts

Lexeme: L1122

[Wikidata](#)

Description	Value	Source
Lemma	dog	
Language	English	
Lexical category	noun	
Word stem		
Derived from		
Homographs	dog	

[Edit on query.Wikidata.org](#)

Form	Features
dog	singular
dogs	plural

[Edit on query.Wikidata.org](#)

Sense	Glosses	Sense image
L1122-S1	anjing // mamífero doméstico // domesticated mammal related to the wolf // huisdier dat afstamt van de wolf // mamífero usado como animal de estimação e parente dos lobos // домашнее животное отряда собачьих // zwierzę domowe spokrewnione z wilkiem // adupan	
L1122-S2	tool in engineering	

Linguistic Linked Open Data in Wikidata: Example Query synonyms of the word “film” in English

Wikidata Query Service Beispiele Hilfe Weitere Werkzeuge Abfragegenerator Deutsch

Abfragehelfer

+ Filter

+ Anzeigen

Begrenzung

```

1 SELECT * {
2   VALUES ?lemma1 {'film'@en}
3   ?lexeme1 wikibase:lemma ?lemma1 . # get lexemes that share the lemma "film" (resulting in the noun and verb form of the word)
4   ?lexeme1 ontolex:sense ?sense1 . # get senses for each lexeme (resulting in movie and membrane senses of the noun film)
5   ?sense1 wdt:P5973 ?sense2 . # get synonymous senses belonging to other lexemes (resulting in a sense of the lexeme motion picture)
6   ?lexeme2 wikibase:lemma ?lemma2 . # then, from all lemmas belonging to any lexeme
7   ?lexeme2 ontolex:sense ?sense2 . # get those that have senses we've found to be synonymous with film
8 }

```

2 Ergebnisse in 245 ms Code Herunterladen Link

lexeme1	lemma1	sense1	sense2	lexeme2	lemma2
Q wd:L1271	film	wd:L1271-S1	wd:L2043-S1	Q wd:L2043	movie
Q wd:L1271	film	wd:L1271-S1	wd:L2046-S1	Q wd:L2046	motion picture

<https://w.wiki/74eh>

Linguistic Linked Open Data in Wikidata: Ordia Tool

<https://ordia.toolforge.org/>

Search after lemma or for **Ordia** Languages Aspects Tools Statistics

Languages

Show entries Search:

Number of lexemes	Language	Description
213617	German	West Germanic language spoken mainly in Central Europe
101780	Russian	East Slavic language
83210	Estonian	Uralic language
72956	English	West Germanic language
67313	Malayalam	Dravidian language of India
56206	Latin	Indo-European language of the Italic branch
43313	Modern Greek	dialects and varieties of the Greek language spoken in the modern era
43007	Spanish	Romantic language originating in the Iberian Peninsula
41127	Swedish	North Germanic language spoken in Sweden and Finland
33666	Bokmål	one of two official written standards for the Norwegian language

[Edit on query.Wikidata.org](#)

Showing 1 to 10 of 1,105 entries Previous 2 3 4 5 ... 111 Next

Outlook: Paleographic Linked Open Data in Wikidata

Idea: Collect all signs from written and non-written scripts in Wikidata.

Also collect their etymology across space and time

Character: (Q87555102) <https://ordia.toolforge.org/>

[Wikidata](#)

Description	Value	Source
Label		
Script	cuneiform	
Instance of	cuneiform sign	
Instance of	Unicode character	
Described in	Manuel D'Epigraphie Akkadienne	
Described in	Sumerisches Lexikon	
Described in	Mesopotamisches Zeichenlexikon (2004 Edition)	
Described in	Hethitisches Zeichenlexikon	
Described in	Altbabylonische Zeichenliste	

[Edit on query.Wikidata.org](#)

Form	Timeperiod	Image
Cuneiform Sign Variant of CUNEIFORM SIGN ARAD (Neo Assyrian)	Neo Assyrian Period	
Cuneiform Sign Variant ARAD (Old Assyrian)	Old-Assyrian period	
Cuneiform Sign Variant ARAD (Akkadian)	Old Babylonian Period // Akkad period	

PaleOrdia: View paleographic sign variants in Wikidata: Cuneiform

<https://situx.github.io/paleordia/>

Hands On: Wikidata

<https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/workshop-osf24-mainz>

<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/workshop-osf24-mainz/>

Example: Hospitals in Germany as Map

Example: International Airports in Germany as Map

Example: Museums in Germany as Map

Example: Museums (natural history) in Germany as Map

Example: Archaeological Sites in RLP as Map with images

Example: Caves with prehistoric art as Map with images

Example: castrum (Roman fortification)

Example: Limes castrum (Roman fortification)

Example: Samian Ware Findspots

Example: Samian Ware Kiln Sites

Example: Samian Ware Kiln Regions

Example: Ogham Stone Sites (Irish Provinces)

Example: Ogham Stone Sites (Dingle Peninsula)

Example: Ogham Stone Sites (Dingle Peninsula, “MAQI”)

Example: Holy Wells in Ireland (and named after)

Hands On: FactGrid

<https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/workshop-osf24-mainz>

FactGrid - a database for historians

The screenshot shows the FactGrid website interface. At the top right, there are language options ('English') and a 'Log in' link. Below this is a navigation bar with 'Main Page' and 'Discussion' tabs, and a search bar labeled 'Search FactGrid'. The main content area is titled 'Main Page' and features a 'Welcome!' section. This section includes a circular logo with the text 'FactGrid a database for historians' and a list of languages represented by flags (German, Spanish, French, Italian, Turkish, Chinese). The text below the logo states: 'to the FactGrid database, a project of the Gotha Research Centre operated by the data lab of the University of Erfurt. With the support of Wikimedia Germany we are using a MediaWiki with Wikidata's "wikibase" extension. Our main product are data which we collect on "Items" such as these:'. A list of items follows: Adam Weishaupt and Paris. Below this, it says 'You will need to be logged in to see the "add statement" link with which you can add information in the form of triple based machine readable claims — which everyone can now explore with the SPARQL data mining language, at our Query Service. All FactGrid data are CC0-licensed. You can download any search in various data formats with the aim to explore FactGrid data in other software environments or visualise searches with various tools on our site.' A 'Visit our' section lists links for 'FactGrid FAQ', 'Help Section', 'Terms of Service', and 'Project Section'. The 'Jour fixe' section mentions a weekly meeting on Thursdays at 21:30 CET. The 'QuickStatements' section notes a security feature in the new version. The 'Message Board' section is also visible.

<https://database.factgrid.de/wiki/Hauptseite>

Sample Queries & FactGrid Query Service

- Main page
- Query service
- Sample queries
- Advanced text search
- Recent changes
- Browse
 - FactGrid Viewer
 - KnolBase Browser
 - EntiTree genealogies
- Project Spaces
- Blog
 - Projects historically
 - Projects alphabetically
 - Projects personally
- To Do
- SPARQL Lab
- Items & Properties
 - New Item
 - MergelItems
 - Batch fragments
 - QuickStatements
 - Directory of Properties
 - New Property
 - Data modeling
- Help
- Lexemes
 - New Lexeme
 - Search
- Tools

Project page **Discussion** Read View source View history Search FactGrid

FactGrid:Sample queries

- Help:
- https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:SPARQL_query_service/Wikidata_Query_Help/Result_VIEWS/en
 - <https://en.wikibooks.org/wiki/SPARQL/FILTER>

Contents [hide]

- Looking for people
- Looking for documents
- Looking for dates
- Maps
 - 4.1 Dots
 - 4.2 Lines
- Tables
- Graphs
- Timelines
- Statistics
 - 8.1 Prevent double listings
- Grammatically intricate searches
 - 9.1 Wikimedia sources
 - 9.2 Statements with sources
 - 9.3 Statements with unit information
 - 9.4 Get information from connected items
 - 9.5 Search for specific Qualifiers on a Statement
 - 9.6 Search for all the Qualifiers on Statements with the same property
 - 9.7 You already know one related value
 - 9.8 Looking for a statement - give it with all the qualifying statements
- Missing Statements
- Missing connections
- Wildcards
- State all statements that are made on an item

https://database.factgrid.de/wiki/FactGrid:Sample_queries

The screenshot shows the FactGrid Query interface. At the top, there are navigation options: 'Beispiele', 'Hilfe', and 'Weitere Werkzeuge'. The main area contains a text input field with the placeholder text '(Eine SPARQL-Abfrage eingeben oder eine Beispielabfrage auswählen)'. Below the input field, there is a map view showing a geographical area with a red location marker. The interface is in German, as indicated by the 'Deutsch' language selector in the top right corner.

<https://database.factgrid.de/query/>

Masonic lodges by systems and obediences

Poets in Paris

Adherents of French Prophets and religious affiliations

Houses in Leipzig (Well-Known Text)

Buildings in Koblenz (Mapping Koblenz Project)

Pharmacies in Koblenz (Mapping Koblenz Project)

Hands On: SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

<https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/workshop-osf24-mainz>

SPARQL-Queries

Wikidata Queries in QGIS (here: Holy Wells)

The screenshot shows the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin window. The interface includes a menu bar with 'Linked Data Processing', 'Queryhelfer', 'Einstellungen', and 'Hilfe'. Below the menu are tabs for 'Abfragen', 'Interlinken', and 'Anreicherung (Experimentell)'. The 'Endpoint auswählen:' dropdown is set to 'Wikidata --> ?item ?geo [SPARQL Endpoint]'. The 'Queryvorlagen:' dropdown is set to 'Item+Label', and the 'Layer Name:' is 'holy_wells'. The 'Valid Query' section contains the following SPARQL query:

```
1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?img ?geo ?osm ?namedafterLabel WHERE {  
2   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q1371047, wd:Q126443332.  
3   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img. }  
4   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P625 ?geo. }  
5   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P11693 ?osm. }  
6   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P138 ?namedafter. }  
7   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }  
8 }
```

The 'Filter Concept Results:' field is empty. The 'GeoConcepts (500)' list on the right contains the following items:

- Antarctic field camp (wd:Q4771007)
- Antarctic research station (wd:Q749622)
- Bahá'í temple (wd:Q1568313)
- British overseas territories (wd:Q46395)
- Catholic cathedral (wd:Q56242215)
- Centaur (wd:Q761888)
- Chondrocladia concrescens (wd:Q1828566)
- Christian denomination (wd:Q879146)
- Christian school (wd:Q867738)
- Coche (wd:Q5403750)
- Conservatory of departmental relevance ...
- Ecclesiastical circumscription immediately ...
- French overseas collectivity (wd:Q719487)
- French wine (wd:Q630531)
- Gendarmerie barracks (wd:Q83554028)
- Gregorian telescope (wd:Q742318)
- Mars crater (wd:Q1475691)
- Mercury crater (wd:Q76833930)
- NOAA Weather Radio station ...
- National Monument of the United States ...
- National Park of the United States ...
- National Reserve (wd:Q6978070)
- National Wildlife Refuge (wd:Q1410668)
- One Earth Ecoregion (wd:Q124221947)
- Plinian eruption (wd:Q747501)
- Protestant church building (wd:Q56242063)
- Roman Catholic metropolitan archdiocese ...
- S-42 (wd:Q1887138)
- Scenic Reserve (wd:Q63248569)
- Sekolah Menengah Atas (wd:Q97598588)
- Sekolah Menengah Pertama (wd:Q97500812)
- Surtseyan eruption (wd:Q1060842)

At the bottom, there are buttons for 'Gespeicherte Queries: ChristSch', 'Query laden', 'Queryname:', and 'Query speichern'. A 'Layer hinzufügen' button is also present. The 'Language for query results:' dropdown is set to 'English (en)'.

Wikidata Queries in QGIS (here: Holy Wells)

Wikidata Queries in QGIS (here: Holy Wells)

id	img	itemLabel	namedafterLabel	osm	
109	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126923120	NULL	Kilmog Holy Well	friar	NULL
110	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126919273	NULL	Friar's Well	friar	NULL
111	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126491170	NULL	Q126491170	head	NULL
112	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126454486	NULL	Well of the head	head	8515246136
113	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126454486	NULL	Well of the head	headache	8515246136
114	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126655791	NULL	Caereeachth Well	herd	NULL
115	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126472909	NULL	Trinity Well	Holy Trinity	NULL
116	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126374490	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	Trinity Well	Holy Trinity	11942593399
117	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126438084	NULL	Holy Trinity Well	Holy Trinity	8517739108
118	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126486274	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	John's Well	John the Baptist	8539018118
119	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126474774	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	St John's Well	John the Baptist	8567014803
120	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126456561	NULL	St. John's Well	John the Baptist	6535302216
121	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126472933	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	St. James's Well	Kings River	8522332218
122	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121840779	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	St. Lachtain's Well (Toberlactain)	Lachtin mac Tarbin	NULL
123	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q127048193	NULL	Saint Laurence's Well	Lawrence of Rome	NULL
124	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126454422	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	St Leonard's Well	Leonard of Noblac	7412516778
125	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126949808	NULL	Loughman's Well	Loughman	NULL
126	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q122303936	NULL	Saint Luke's Well	Luke	8526425065
127	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126478503	NULL	St. Mocuille's Well	Mac Cuill	8522349432
128	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126454603	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	St. Mogue's Well	Máedóc of Ferns	7995685476
129	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126485951	NULL	St. Margaret's Well	Margaret the Virgin	8515639045
130	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126476522	NULL	St. Martin's Well	Martin of Tours	8490582674
131	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126890179	NULL	St. Mary's Well	Mary	NULL
132	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126646306	NULL	Lady's Well	Mary	NULL
133	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126645328	NULL	Q126645328	Mary	NULL
134	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126888828	NULL	Lady's Well	Mary	NULL
135	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126617074	NULL	Our Lady's Well	Mary	NULL
136	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126499565	NULL	Tobar Muire	Mary	11973631439
137	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126478980	NULL	Lady's Well	Mary	NULL

FactGrid Queries in QGIS (please do a HOTFIX)

The screenshot shows a GitHub interface. At the top, an issue titled "FactGrid triplestoreconf.json HOTFIX #41" is marked as "Open". It was opened by user "florianthiery" 2 minutes ago and has 0 comments. Below the issue title, a comment from "florianthiery" (Member) is shown. The comment text reads: "The FactGrid triplestoreconf.json uses HTTP instead of HTTPS for the prefixes". It lists two bullet points: "wd": "http://database.factgrid.de/entity/" and "wdt": "http://database.factgrid.de/prop/direct/". The comment continues: "Please update triplestoreconf.json and triplestoreconf_personal.json (in the local conf folder) as shown in https://gist.github.com/florianthiery/0504f2faf402905aeb557be6430eede0 to fix this issue and query FactGrid. The conf folder is in Windows at "...\AppData\Roaming\QGIS\QGIS3\profiles\default\python\plugins\sparqlunicorn\conf". At the bottom of the comment area, a pull request titled "Update triplestoreconf.json #42" is shown as "Merged". It was merged by "florianthiery" 1 minute ago, merging 1 commit into the "master" branch from the "factgrid-triplestoreconf" branch.

FactGrid triplestoreconf.json HOTFIX #41

Open florianthiery opened this issue 2 minutes ago · 0 comments

florianthiery commented 2 minutes ago · edited

Member

The FactGrid triplestoreconf.json uses HTTP instead of HTTPS for the prefixes

- "wd": "http://database.factgrid.de/entity/"
- "wdt": "http://database.factgrid.de/prop/direct/"

Please update **triplestoreconf.json** and **triplestoreconf_personal.json** (in the local **conf** folder) as shown in <https://gist.github.com/florianthiery/0504f2faf402905aeb557be6430eede0> to fix this issue and query FactGrid.

The *conf* folder is in Windows at "...\AppData\Roaming\QGIS\QGIS3\profiles\default\python\plugins\sparqlunicorn\conf"

Update triplestoreconf.json #42

Merged florianthiery merged 1 commit into master from factgrid-triplestoreconf 1 minute ago

FactGrid Queries in QGIS (here: Buildings in Koblenz)

The screenshot shows the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin interface. The main window is titled "SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin" and has a menu bar with "Linked Data Processing", "Queryhelfer", "Einstellungen", and "Hilfe". Below the menu bar are three tabs: "Abfragen", "Interlinken", and "Anreicherung (Experimentell)".

The "Abfragen" tab is active. It contains the following fields and controls:

- Endpoint auswählen:** A dropdown menu showing "Factgrid --> ?item ?geo [SPARQL Endpoint]" and a "Quick Add RDF Resource" button.
- Filter Concept Results:** An empty text input field.
- Queryvorlagen:** A dropdown menu showing "Item+Label".
- Layer Name:** A text input field containing "buildings".

The main area is a text editor with a "Valid Query" label. It contains the following SPARQL query:

```
1 SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?layerLabel WHERE {  
2 ?item wdt:P131 wd:Q922978.  
3 ?item wdt:P2 ?layer.  
4 ?item wdt:P48 ?geo.  
5 SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }  
6 } ORDER BY ?typeLabel
```

At the bottom of the text editor, there are buttons for "Gespeicherte Queries:", "Query laden", "Queryname:", and "Query speichern". Below these is a "Layer hinzufügen" button.

On the right side of the interface, there is a list of "GeoConcepts (293)". The list includes various concepts such as "Abandoned village (wd:Q394100)", "Abbey (wd:Q23241)", "Academic Gymnasium (wd:Q251696)", "Academy for young noblemen (wd:Q456641)", "Academy of sciences (wd:Q451465)", "Administrative district (wd:Q164495)", "Administrative quarter in Paris (since 1860) ...", "Aid agency (wd:Q424989)", "Amt (wd:Q466827)", "Ancient settlement (wd:Q389596)", "Archipelago (wd:Q183624)", "Architectural structure (wd:Q160381)", "Archive (wd:Q11)", "Arrondissement of Paris (1795-1860) ...", "Arrondissement of Paris (since 1860) ...", "Art museum (wd:Q484898)", "Art school (wd:Q267016)", "Association (wd:Q469373)", "Astronomical observatory (wd:Q180745)", "Autonomous community of Spain ...", "Barony (wd:Q702926)", "Barony (wd:Q77481)", "Basic object (wd:Q22)", "Battle (wd:Q256340)", "Beiderstädtischen Amt (wd:Q749952)", "Boarding school (wd:Q144989)", "Body of water (wd:Q550497)", "Bonne ville de l'Empire français (wd:Q448326)", "Border (wd:Q255218)", "Botanical garden (wd:Q165188)", "Building (wd:Q533576)", and "Burschenschaft (wd:Q255076)".

At the bottom right of the interface, there is a "Language for query results:" dropdown menu set to "English (en)".

FactGrid Queries in QGIS (here: Buildings in Koblenz)

id	itemLabel	layerLabel
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949314	Koblenz, Altengraben 13a	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949314	Koblenz, Altengraben 13a	architectural heritage monument
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959287	Koblenz, Altengraben 15	Residential building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959287	Koblenz, Altengraben 15	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959287	Koblenz, Altengraben 15	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949315	Koblenz, Altengraben 17	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949315	Koblenz, Altengraben 17	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949315	Koblenz, Altengraben 17	architectural heritage monument
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959288	Koblenz, Altengraben 18	Residential building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959288	Koblenz, Altengraben 18	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959288	Koblenz, Altengraben 18	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959289	Koblenz, Altengraben 20	Residential building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959289	Koblenz, Altengraben 20	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959289	Koblenz, Altengraben 20	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949316	Koblenz, Altengraben 25	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949316	Koblenz, Altengraben 25	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949316	Koblenz, Altengraben 25	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949316	Koblenz, Altengraben 25	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949316	Koblenz, Altengraben 25	architectural heritage monument
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q949316	Koblenz, Altengraben 25	architectural heritage monument
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q946970	Koblenz, Altengraben 26	Residential building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q946970	Koblenz, Altengraben 26	Business address
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q946970	Koblenz, Altengraben 26	Building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959290	Koblenz, Altengraben 28	Residential building
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959290	Koblenz, Altengraben 28	Real estate
https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q959290	Koblenz, Altengraben 28	Building

nomisma.org Mints

The screenshot displays the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin interface. The main window is titled "SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin" and contains several panels:

- Endpoint auswählen:** Set to "Nomisma --> ?item ?lat ?lon [SPARQL Endpoint]".
- Queryvorlagen:** Set to "100 Random Places".
- Layer Name:** Set to "nmo:mint".
- SPARQL Query:**

```
1 SELECT ?item ?lat ?lon WHERE {  
2 ?item a <http://nomisma.org/ontology#Mint> .  
3 ?item geo:location ?loc .  
4 ?loc wgs84_pos:lat ?lat .  
5 ?loc wgs84_pos:long ?lon .  
6 }
```
- Filter Concept Results:** A search bar for filtering results.
- GeoConcepts (4):** A list of concepts: "nmo:Mint", "nmo:Region", "skos:Concept", and "wgs84_pos:SpatialThing".
- Map:** A map of Europe and the Mediterranean region with numerous grey circular markers representing the results of the SPARQL query. The markers are densely clustered in Western and Central Europe.
- Bottom Panel:** Includes "Gespeicherte Queries:" with a dropdown, "Query laden", "Queryname:", "Query speichern", and a "Layer hinzufügen" button.

nomisma.org - All coins found in Northamptonshire, ordered chronologically by issue

The screenshot displays the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin interface. The main window shows a SPARQL query for finding coins in Northamptonshire, ordered by issue date. The query is as follows:

```
1 PREFIX crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>
2 SELECT ?item ?type ?date ?place ?lat ?lon WHERE {
3 ?item nmo:hasFindspot/crm:P7_took_place_at/crm:P89_falls_within ?place ;
4 nmo:hasTypeSeriesItem ?type ;
5 a nmo:NumismaticObject .
6 ?place crm:P89_falls_within+ <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q23115> .
7 ?type nmo:hasEndDate ?date .
8 ?place geo:location ?loc .
9 ?loc geo:lat ?lat ;
10 geo:long ?lon .
11 } ORDER BY ASC(?date)
```

The interface also shows a map of Northamptonshire with various towns labeled, including Peterborough, Huntingdon, Bedford, Milton Keynes, and Northampton. The map is overlaid with a layer of coin locations, represented by colored diamonds. A legend in the bottom right corner identifies the layers and the date ranges for the coins:

- unicorn_Northamptonshire
- 101 - 0
- 0 - 20
- 20 - 40
- 40 - 189
- 189 - 323
- 323 - 402
- Esri Standard

The word "date" is written vertically next to the date range legend.

Roman Open Data - Gauloise 4 Amphoras

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Roman Open Data --> ?item ?lat ?lon [SPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: 100 Random Geometries Layer Name: rod_Gauloise4

Valid Query

```
1 PREFIX : <http://www.semanticweb.org/ontologies/2015/1/EPNet-ONTOP_Ontology#>
2 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
3 PREFIX dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
4 SELECT ?item ?amphtype ?lat ?lon (count(?item) as ?count)
5 WHERE {
6   ?amph a :Amphora .
7   ?amph :hasAmphoraType ?amphtypeo .
8   ?amphtypeo dcterms:title ?amphtype .
9   FILTER (?amphtype = "Gauloise 4")
10  ?amph :carries ?inscription .
11  ?amph :hasFindingPlace ?findplace .
12  ?findplace :fallsWithin ?mun .
13  ?mun a :Municipality .
14  ?mun dcterms:title ?item .
15  ?mun :hasLatitude ?lat .
16  ?mun :hasLongitude ?lon .
17 } ORDER BY ?item DESC(?count)
```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen Language for query results: English (en)

Squirrel Store - Hadrian's Wall Forts

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: [Research Squirrel Engineers Triplestore --> ?item ?geo](#) [G] [Quick Add RDF Resource](#) Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: HWforts

Valid Query

```

1 SELECT ?item ?geo ?name ?latin_name ?typeLabel WHERE {
2   ?item rdf:type hw:Fort .
3   ?item geosparql:hasGeometry ?item_geom .
4   ?item_geom geosparql:asWKT ?geo .
5   ?item hw:name ?name .
6   ?item hw:latin_name ?latin_name .
7   ?item a ?type .
8   ?type rdfs:label ?typeLabel .
9   FILTER NOT EXISTS {
10    FILTER (?typeLabel = "Fort"@en)
11  }
12 }

```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname:

	id	latin_name	name	typeLabel
1	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#19	Bibra (?)	Beckfoot	Cumbrian Coast
2	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#4	Condercum	Benwell	Hadrian's Wall
3	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#33	Fanum Cocidi (?)	Bewcastle	Outpost Fort
4	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#38	Vinovia	Binchester	Support Fort
5	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#12	Banna	Birdoswald	Stanegate
6	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#36	Blatobulgium	Birrens	Outpost Fort
7	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#18	Maia	Bowness-on-So...	Hadrian's Wall
8	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#14	-	Brampton Old ...	Stanegate
9	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#39	Brocavum	Brougham	Support Fort
10	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#16	Aballava	Burgh-by-Sands	Hadrian's Wall
11	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#20	-	Burrow Walls	Cumbrian Coast
12	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#23	Luguvalium	Carlisle	Stanegate
13	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#7	Brocolitia	Carrawburgh	Hadrian's Wall
14	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#11	Magna	Carvoran	Stanegate
15	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#13	Camboglanna	Castlesteads	Hadrian's Wall
16	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#27	Concangis	Chester-le-Street	Support Fort
17	http://hadrrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#8	Cilurnum	Chesters	Hadrian's Wall

GeoConcepts (17)

- Watchtower
- hw:CoastalSite
- hw:Cumbrian_Coast
- hw:Curtain_wall
- hw:Fort

unicorn HWforts

- Cumbrian Coast
- Hadrian's Wall
- Outpost Fort
- Stanegate
- Support Fort

OpenStreetMap H.O.T.

Ogham Store - Ogham Stones with *MAQI* (son of)

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen:

Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: Layer Name:

Valid Query

```
1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?geo ?itemLabel ?stone ?stoneLabel ?readingLabel WHERE {
2 ?stone oghamonto:shows ogham:OW6.
3 ?stone rdfs:label ?stoneLabel .
4 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
5 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
6 ?item rdfs:label ?itemLabel .
7 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?geom_obj .
8 ?geom_obj geosparql:asWKT ?geo .
9 ?stone oghamonto:carries ?inscription .
10 ?inscription oghamonto:identifiedAs ?reading .
11 ?reading rdfs:label ?readingLabel .
12 FILTER(regex(?readingLabel, "MAQI"))
13 }
```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results:

GeoConcepts (9)

- Barony
- Barony (oghamonto:Barony)
- County
- County (oghamonto:County)
- Feature (geosparql:Feature)
- Geographic Location ...
- Location
- Ogham Site (oghamonto:OghamSite)
- Pleiades Place (Place)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots via Solid Pod

The image shows two overlapping windows from the QGIS SPARQLing Unicorn plugin. The top window, titled "Configure Own RDF Resource", is used for setting up a new RDF resource. It includes fields for "Typ der RDF Resource" (set to "RDF Resource als URI"), "RDF Resource Name" ("Campanian Ignimbrite (SolidPod)"), and "RDF Ressourcen URL" (https://fuzzy-sl.solidweb.org/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/ci_full.ttl). There are also options for authentication (set to "HTTP BASIC") and a "Hinzufügen" button.

The bottom window, titled "SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin", displays a SPARQL query and its results. The query is:

```
1 SELECT ?item ?geo ?label ?ref ?spatialType WHERE {
2 ?item a <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Site> .
3 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
4 ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/hasReference> ?ref .
5 ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/spatialType> ?spatialType .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 }
```

The results pane on the right shows a list of "Site" entities under the "GeoConcepts (4)" tab. The list includes:

- Acerra Sink (cisite_1)
- Acqua Fidia (cisite_2)
- Balta Alba (Romania) (cisite_57)
- Batajnica (cisite_104)
- Bratul Borcea (Romania) (cisite_56)
- Capezzano (cisite_3)
- Casola (cisite_4)
- Castelcivita Cave (cisite_5)
- Copcecchia (cisite_6)
- Crvena Stijena (Montenegro) (cisite_51)
- Cuma (cisite_7)
- Dobrogea (Romania) (cisite_53)
- Dunaszekcsó (cisite_103)
- Franchthi Cave (Greece) (cisite_45)
- Golema Pesht Cave near Zdunje ...
- Gulf of Naples (cisite_8)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots via Solid Pod

unicorn_sites — Objekte gesamt:104, gefiltert: 104, gewählt: 0

	id	label	ref	spatialType
1	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_1	Acerra Sink	Scandone et al., 1991	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Sink
2	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_2	Acqua Fidia	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
3	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_57	Balta Alba (Romania)	Pötter et al., 2021	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
4	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_104	Batajnica	Obreht, I. et al. (2017), Fig. 1	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
5	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_104	Batajnica	Buggle, B. et al. (2013)	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
6	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_104	Batajnica	Buggle, B. et al. (2014)	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
7	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_56	Bratul Borcea (Romania)	Pötter et al., 2021	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
8	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_3	Capeziano	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/InhabitedPlace
9	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_4	Casola	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/InhabitedPlace
10	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_5	Castelcivita Cave	Fedele et al., 2008	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
11	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_5	Castelcivita Cave	Giaccio et al., 2008	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
12	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_6	Copcechia	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
13	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_51	Crvena Stijena (Montenegro)	Morley & Woodward, 2011	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
14	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_51	Crvena Stijena (Montenegro)	Morley & Woodward, 2011	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
15	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_7	Cuma	Pappalardo et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
16	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_53	Dobrogea (Romania)	Fitzsimmons et al., 2014	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Plateau
17	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_53	Dobrogea (Romania)	Fitzsimmons et al., 2013	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Plateau
18	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_103	Dunazekcsó	Obreht, I. et al. (2017), Fig. 1	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
19	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_103	Dunazekcsó	Újvári, G. Et al. (2016)	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
20	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_45	Franchthi Cave (Greece)	Fedele et al., 2003	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
21	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_45	Franchthi Cave (Greece)	Fedele et al., 2003	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
22	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_50	Golema Pesht Cave near Zdu...	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
23	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_50	Golema Pesht Cave near Zdu...	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
24	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_8	Gulf of Naples	Arienzo et al., 2009	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Bight
25	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_65	Haua-Feah (Libya)	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
26	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_65	Haua-Feah (Libya)	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
27	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_61	Kisiljevo (Serbia)	Baykal et al., 2018	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
28	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_46	Klissoura (Greece)	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
29	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_60	Kostenki (Russia)	Fedele et al., 2003	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/InhabitedPlace
30	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/ciste_59	Kostenki-Borshevo (Russia)	Fedele et al., 2008	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite

Alle Objekte anzeigen

Transformation from CSV / GeoJSON into RDF (e.g. GeoSPARQL)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot CSV to RDF

id	label	desc	literature	wkt	certainty	certaintyinfo
1	Acerra Sink	CI findspot related from literature	Scandone et al., 1991	POINT(14.3624 40.9489)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
2	Acqua Fidia	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.6983 40.9285)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
3	Capezzano	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7680 40.7119)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
4	Casola	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.5259 40.6993)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
5	Castelvita Cave	CI findspot related from literature	Fedele et al., 2008;Giaccio et al., 2008	POINT(15.2092 40.4956)	fs:high	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
6	Copecchia	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7662 40.7198)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
7	Cuma	CI findspot related from literature	Pappalardo et al., 1999	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
8	Gulf of Naples	CI findspot related from literature	Arienzo et al., 2009	POINT(14.2559 40.7192)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
9	Lago Patria (Naples)	CI findspot related from literature	Civetta et al., 1997;Scandone et al., 1991	POINT(14.0366 40.9260)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
10	Marina di Cassano (Naples)	CI findspot related from literature	Civetta et al., 1997	POINT(14.3998 40.6385)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
11	Massaquano (Naples)	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.4476 40.6619)	fs:medium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
12	Monte Echia (Naples)	CI findspot related from literature	Pappalardo et al., 1999	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fs:medium	scientific paper
13	Lago Grande di Monticchio	CI findspot related from literature	Narcisi, 1996	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fs:medium	scientific paper
14	Monticchio (Bagni)	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fs:medium	scientific paper
15	Monticchio Lakes	CI findspot related from literature	Brauer et al., 1999	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fs:medium	scientific paper
16	Murge Plateau	CI findspot related from literature	Giaccio et al., 2008	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fs:medium	scientific paper

Hinzuzufügende Elemente wählen | cifindspots_part_full

C:\git\workshop-osf24-mainz\src\cifindspots_part_full.csv

Suche...

Element	Beschreibung
Point (71)	

Alle wählen Alle abwählen

Optionen

- Layer zu einer Gruppe hinzufügen
- System und interne Tabellen anzeigen
- Leere Vektorlayer anzeigen

Layer hinzufügen Abbrechen

QGIS3

Dieser Layer scheint keine Projektionsangaben zu besitzen. Die Projektion dieses Layers wird auf die des Projektes voreingestellt. Sie können es jedoch unten durch auswählen einer anderen Projektion überschreiben.

Vordefiniertes KBS

Filter

Kürzlich benutzte Koordinatenbezugssysteme

Koordinatensystem	AutoritätsID
WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator	EPSG:3857
WGS 84	EPSG:4326

Vordefinierte Koordinatenreferenzsystem Veraltete KBS verbergen

Koordinatenbezugssystem	AutoritätsID
Voirol 1879 (Paris)	EPSG:4821
Wake Island 1952	EPSG:4733
Wallis (MOP 1976) geographiq...	IGNF:WALL76G
Wallis (MOP 1978) geographiq...	IGNF:WALL78G
WGS 66	EPSG:4760
WGS 72	EPSG:4322
WGS 72BE	EPSG:4324
WGS 84	EPSG:4326

WGS 84

Eigenschaften

- Geographisch (verwendet Längen- und Breitengrad für Koordinaten)
- Dynamisch (hängt von einem Datum ab, das nicht plattenfixiert ist)
- Überirdischer Körper: Earth
- Basierend auf World Geodetic

OK Abbrechen Hilfe

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot CSV to RDF

cfindspots_part_full — Objekte gesamt:71, gefiltert: 71, gewählt: 0

id	label	desc	literature	wkt	certainty	certaintyinfo	relatedto	relatedtohow	source	sourcetype	spatialtype	methodtype	agent	methoddesc
1	Acerra Sink	CI findspot rela...	Scandone et al., ...	POINT(14.3624 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	fspartyMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslSink	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
2	Acqua Fidia	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.6983 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://www.op...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslUnknownCat...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
3	Capezzano	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7680 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
4	Casola	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.5259 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://www.op...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
5	Castelcivita Cave	CI findspot rela...	Fedele et al., 20...	POINT(15.2092 ...	fslhigh	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslCave	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
6	Copcechia	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7662 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslUnknownCat...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
7	Cuma	CI findspot rela...	Pappalardo et a...	POINT(14.0560 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslUnknownCat...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
8	Gulf of Naples	CI findspot rela...	Aienzo et al., 2...	POINT(14.2559 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslBight	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
9	Lago Patria (Na...	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.0366 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
10	Marina di Cassa...	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3998 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslBight	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
11	Massaquano (N...	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.4476 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
12	Monte Echia (N...	CI findspot rela...	Pappalardo et a...	POINT(14.2479 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslMountain	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
13	Lago Grande di...	CI findspot rela...	Narcisi, 1996	POINT(15.6057 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslLake	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
14	Monticchio (Ba...	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(15.5699 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
15	Monticchio Lakes	CI findspot rela...	Brauer et al., 20...	POINT (15.6098...	fslhigh	findspot menti...	https://www.op...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslLake	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
16	Murge Plateau	CI findspot rela...	Giaccio et al., ...	POINT(16.2833 ...	fslow	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslPlateau	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
17	Naples	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 1996	POINT(14.2080 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
18	Pacognano	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.4347 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://www.op...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
19	Paglicci Cave	CI findspot rela...	Giaccio et al., 2...	POINT(15.6150 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslCave/fslArch...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
20	Pellezzano	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7546 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
21	Penta	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7979 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
22	Phlegraean Fields	CI findspot rela...	Orsi et al., 1996...	POINT(14.1402 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslSupervolcano	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
23	Ponti Rossi (Na...	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.2594 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	fspartyMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslUnknownCat...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
24	Pozzuoli Bay	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 1996	POINT(14.0890 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslBight	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
25	Pucara	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.6459 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://openstre...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslUnknownCat...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
26	Punta Marmolite	CI findspot rela...	Pappalardo et a...	POINT(14.1489 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	fslspatialClose...	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslUnknownCat...	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
27	Sant' Agata dei ...	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3733 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
28	Sant' Angelo a ...	CI findspot rela...	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7402 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
29	San Marco	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3381 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
30	San Nicola La S...	CI findspot rela...	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3313 ...	fslmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fslPaperDesc	fslPaper	fslInhabitedPlace	fslGeoreferenci...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot CSV to RDF


```
suni:c434e049-c2ab-4308-8d6b-b3247b5ffba0 a suni:d1f06db3-dd8c-4b96-a360-f28909f76c65 ;
suni:agent <http://orcid.org/0009-0008-2877-3204> ;
suni:certainty "fsl:medium"^^xsd:string ;
suni:certaintyinfo "Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76: "In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south of the Danube River. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary-age limestone basement rocks (Munteanu et al., 2008), which were the target of earlier quarrying activities."; Pötter et al. (2021), p.5: "The Urluia (URL) LPS is located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea (Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obreht et al., 2017).""^^xsd:string ;
suni:desc "CI findspot related from literature"^^xsd:string ;
suni:label "Urluia (Romania)"^^xsd:string ;
suni:literature "Fitzsimmons et al., 2014;Fitzsimmons et al., 2013;Obreht et al., 2017;Pötter et al., 2021"^^xsd:string ;
suni:methoddesc "set a representative point based on scientific papers using Google Maps"^^xsd:string ;
suni:methodtype "fsl:Georeferencing"^^xsd:string ;
suni:relatedto <http://sws.geonames.org/664132;http://openstreetmap.org/way/84975654> ;
suni:relatedtohow "skos:closeMatch"^^xsd:string ;
suni:source "fsl:PaperDesc"^^xsd:string ;
suni:sourcetype "fsl:Paper"^^xsd:string ;
suni:spatialtype "fsl:InhabitedPlace"^^xsd:string ;
suni:wkt "POINT(27.9021 44.0947)"^^xsd:string ;
geo:hasGeometry suni:c434e049-c2ab-4308-8d6b-b3247b5ffba0_geom .
```

```
suni:c434e049-c2ab-4308-8d6b-b3247b5ffba0_geom a geo:Point ;
geo:asWKT "Point (27.902100000000000079 44.0947000000000000312)"^^geo:wktLiteral .
```

European River Network GeoJSON to RDF

NAME	Shape_Leng
Danube	2770357,36328
Douro	816245,218931
Ebro	826990,879516
Elbe	1087288,26667
Guadalquivir	599758,347758
Guadiana	1063055,37701
Loire	944755,381131
Nemunas	689209,621531
Odra	823753,80297
Rhine	1159962,39349
Rhone	910617,937531
Sava	625964,046091
Seine	673648,436798

European River Network GeoJSON to RDF

```
suni:5eb80411-ee91-47ef-a3a2-89c6440709b5 a suni:7babd7e6-5fc0-457f-8e46-d37bcb9c9d7b ;  
suni:NAME "Rhine"^^xsd:string ;  
suni:Shape_Leng 1.159962e+06 ;  
geo:hasGeometry suni:5eb80411-ee91-47ef-a3a2-89c6440709b5_geom .
```

```
suni:5eb80411-ee91-47ef-a3a2-89c6440709b5_geom a geo:MultiLineString ;  
geo:asWKT "MultiLineString ((5.94425373459836237 51.94878151289067603, 5.95763502500831166 51.92072893309910597, 5.99252667260233185 51.8943079853457121,  
6.0197039927329099 51.87012905448126787, 6.02354236358268835 51.86903159930916729, 6.03614239689617094 51.86578946616741348, 6.04172145893227608  
51.86470845172616606, 6.04784263528278299 51.86363235561832141, 6.0519818996624748 51.86236926894400767, 6.06206365752319343 51.85696996339164855,  
6.06494240075981139 51.85552874023783687, 6.07239335244463962 51.85561952215852699, 6.07286273716284164 51.85535107166987245, 6.07754296641921421  
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6.12164486079504666 51.84706988341645939, 6.13262405640909503 51.84545117517711788, 6.13784452728666619 51.84383225306831378, 6.14540525979273333  
51.84203121366012113, 6.16016641841395263 51.83933140287626173, 6.16430455715529035 51.83789009429020922, 6.16808628306268236 51.83699181983632798,  
6.17546517479860579 51.83446983022260923, 6.18140614999137838 51.83231346398925865, 6.18896681263495196 51.83123263177485995, 6.19634626013637213  
51.83087226222865951, 6.20174648752750901 51.82996975418765118, 6.20714597872273899 51.83032938553009217, 6.21884614338669994 51.83032981165113284,  
6.22442677434776304 51.82996969819716782, 6.23252644524000043 51.82889334104307011, 6.23972701365957513 51.82835070208100348, 6.24494728188943693  
51.82673183440196851, 6.24854754719583336 51.82583352056782644, 6.25754731491432725 51.82295130944225292, 6.26708729566186395 51.81935320933103384,  
6.27140764268719941 51.81683192407359684, 6.28004801673353263 51.81322915398144602, 6.28994795575870835 51.80855007421418179, 6.2926474281671414  
51.80693087375526318, 6.29588781294047006 51.80333281153805558, 6.30326910612278812 51.79955292261365685, 6.30794878687197702 51.7961323415815329,  
6.31316949192955423 51.79091090459529312, 6.32108890531169365 51.78083249178777692, 6.32378961524695526 51.77489072067231035, 6.32954984546400112  
51.76696927594473152, 6.33314982703458274 51.76373143936950783, 6.33566962972964731 51.76193016318202211, 6.33908897736387544 51.76012898172502474,  
6.34556984722843342 51.75742934925625605, 6.35456898091508027 51.7559884521550444, 6.36050982326214509 51.75562814849720894, 6.36969054207122731  
51.75634875449595285, 6.37364910507663129 51.75634878069891442, 6.38319004608463203 51.75742959170322166, 6.39057094335437093 51.75761224393758653,  
6.39722994403617573 51.75742927359260648, 6.40209048182195062 51.75653118197054425, 6.41019022382963399 51.75328899186865073, 6.41523147596722243  
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6.41829085573518121 51.7345685729053173, 6.41055007362039309 51.72196875042985198, 6.41055022125778873 51.71782795915469677, 6.41433064649456242  
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```


RDF HTML-Documentation

Roman Province Borders to HTML

id	label
1	1 Reatia-Noricum
2	2 Raetia-Noricum
3	3 Italia
4	4 Creta et Cyrene
5	5 Baetica-Tarraconensis
6	6 Mauretania Tingetana
7	7 Lusitania-Baetica
8	8 Lusitania-Tarraconensis
9	9 Tarraconensis-Gallia Narbonensis
10	10 Creta et Cyrene-Africa Proconsularis
11	11 Mauretania Tingetana
12	12 Africa Proconsularis-Mauretania Caesarensis
13	13 Britannia
14	14 Alpes Poeniae-Gallia Belgica
15	15 Arabia
16	16 Aegyptus-Creta et Cyrene
17	17 Aegyptus-Creta et Cyrene
18	18 Arabia
19	19 Bytinia et Pontus-Asia
20	20 Asia-Lycia
21	21 Noricum-Barbaricum
22	22 Dalmatia-Moesia
23	23 Macadonia-Moesia
24	24 Macedonia-Achaia
25	25 Thracia-Moesia
26	26 Thracia-Macedonia

Create HTML Documentation from RDF

HTML result (Start Page)

Index page for <http://www.github.com/sparqlunicorn#>

http://www.github.com/sparqlunicorn#suni_dataset powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin OntDoc Script 0.17](#)

Search: Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

This page shows information about linked data resources in HTML. Choose the classtree navigation or search to browse the data

Download VOWL File Download Mini VOWL File

Show entries

Class	Number of Instances	Instance Example
871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2 (suni:871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2) [78]	4	Gallia Belgica-Germania Inferior (suni:011bac95-d80d-412b-b734-bd1a3a5bdc)

- PrimeMeridian (geocrs:PrimeMeridian) [1]
- SpatialObject (gsp:SpatialObject)
- Feature (gsp:Feature)
- 871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2 (suni:871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2)
- Aegyptus-Creta et Cyrene (suni:41bfa2a0-8582-...
- Aegyptus-Creta et Cyrene (suni:975c1740-2e22-...
- Africa Proconsularis-Mauretania Caesarensis (s...
- Alpes Cottae-Alpes Graiae et Poen. (suni:b69c72...
- Alpes Poeniae-Gallia Belgica (suni:b82091f-5d0...
- Alpes Poeniae-Raetia (suni:af4089c9-4bb9-41b1...
- Alpes marines-Alpes (suni:6d0a1abd-7ed7-433c...
- Arabia (suni:f80cba4b-91bf-4ccc-bb49-b6d11405...
- Arabia (suni:fd506cfe-26d2-48fd-b665-6557d58f...
- Asia-Lycia (suni:6b099876-5f96-4111-b3bc-0956...
- Baetica-Tarraconensis (suni:ecd4a284-5f39-45a...
- Britannia (suni:5853ef83-2d77-4b60-9ebd-5057c...
- Bytynia et Pontus-Asia (suni:e6a399fd-2206-430...
- Bytynia et Pontus-Cappadocia (suni:22d97328-4...
- Cappadocia-Armenia (suni:c7434610-6197-4a2f...
- Cilicia-Cappadocia (suni:d35f3c41-2542-4b08-9...
- Creta et Cyrene (suni:71947e99-a3ca-40b2-9d9...
- Creta et Cyrene-Africa Proconsularis (suni:be214...
- Dacia-Barbaricum (suni:38692482-c381-46fa-af1...
- Dalmatia-Moesia (suni:5921f34c-8fd1-4667-8674...
- Dalmatia-Pannonia (suni:6232bfb3-840e-47ef-b1...
- Galatia-Bytynia et Pontus (suni:44a208bf-d85a-4...
- Galatia-Cappadocia (suni:31df4a47-7635-45ce-t...
- Galatia-Cappadocia (suni:92b5934e-6d7b-4841...
- Galatia-Cappadocia (suni:fd692685-b083-47ae-1...
- Galatia-Galicia (suni:477fbc88-0db6-4992-ba6c...
- Gallia Aquitania-Gallia Lugdunensis (suni:08c1b...
- Gallia Aquitania-Gallia Lugdunensis (suni:1e9db...
- Gallia Aquitania-Gallia Lugdunensis (suni:a506b...
- Gallia Belgica-Gallia Narbonensis (suni:ec41e8t...
- Gallia Belgica-Germania Inferior (suni:011bac95...
- Gallia Belgica-Germania Inferior (suni:973c6a5a...
- Gallia Belgica-Raetia (suni:b88abd85-3eb7-459a...
- Gallia Lugdunensis-Alpes (suni:24917928-8b16...
- Gallia Lugdunensis-Gallia Belgica (suni:2a56b57...
- Gallia Lugdunensis-Gallia Belgica (suni:c28f9ba...
- Gallia Lugdunensis-Gallia Narbonensis (suni:25f...

HTML result (Spatial Instances Collection)

871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2 Instances Collection

http://www.github.com/sparqlunicorn#871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2_collection powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin OntDoc Script 0.17

Search: Go Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL) Download Query

Property	Value
type (rdf:type)	FeatureCollection (gsp:FeatureCollection)
label (rdfs:label)	871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2 Instances Collection (rdf:langString) (iso6391.en)
member (rdfs:member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ 78 values • Aegyptus-Creta et Cyrene (suni:411fa2a0-8582-4ef0-a98e-a54965a9547c) • Aegyptus-Creta et Cyrene (suni:975c1740-2a22-4c50-a127-1fe800d6005) • Africa Proconsularis-Mauretania Caesarensis (suni:7f8d220a-10aa-46df-a00f-b338677d3dcf) • Alpes Cotiae-Alpes Graiae et Poen. (suni:b69c72de-95ad-4e8c-96b7-e89cd2b99701) • Alpes Poeninae-Gallia Belgica (suni:b8f2091f-5d01-4de1-9041-bcd6b608ed03) • Alpes Poeninae-Raetia (suni:af4089c9-4bb9-41b8-b856-5d54d48f7f11) • Alpes marinae-Alpes (suni:6d0a1abd-7ed7-433d-a2b8-894dfee284cc) • Arabia (suni:f80cba4b-91bf-4ccc-bb49-b6d114054d94) • Arabia (suni:fd506cfe-26d2-48fd-b665-6557d5059942) • Asia-Lycia (suni:6d099076-5f96-4111-b3bc-095644dc5b8c) • Baetica-Tarconensis (suni:ecd4a284-5f39-45a6-bceb-6d28d20f9135) • Britannia (suni:5853ef83-2d77-4b60-9ebd-5057c11c4422) • Bytynia et Pontus-Asia (suni:e6a399fd-2206-430d-95b3-ae6566172012) • Bytynia et Pontus-Cappadocia (suni:22d97328-4f03-4f83-a87b-ed1cf9a85af0) • Cappadocia-Armenia (suni:c7434610-6197-4a2e-b9d6-ad0deb13b27a) • Cilicia-Cappadocia (suni:d35f3c41-2542-4b08-9a81-b737af751f8e) • Creta et Cyrene (suni:71947e99-a3ca-40b2-9d96-714290ccea65) • Creta et Cyrene-Africa Proconsularis (suni:be2141f9-2eac-4360-91f9-4008d0dc6e59)

GeoClasses: X

Search:

- AxisDirection (geocrs:AxisDirection) [2]
- CoordinateSystemAxis (geocrs:CoordinateSystemAxis) [2]
- Ellipsoid (geocrs:Ellipsoid) [1]
- EllipsoidalCoordinateSystem (geocrs:EllipsoidalCoordinateSystem) [1]
- Entity (prov:Entity) [1]
- GeodeticReferenceFrame (geocrs:GeodeticReferenceFrame) [1]
- GeographicCRS (geocrs:GeographicCRS) [1]
- PlanarCoordinateSystem (geocrs:PlanarCoordinateSystem) [1]
- PrimeMeridian (geocrs:PrimeMeridian) [1]
- SpatialObject (gsp:SpatialObject)
- SpatialReferenceSystem (geocrs:SpatialReferenceSystem) [1]
- Unit (om:Unit) [1]
- Collection (skos:Collection) [1]
- SpatialObjectCollection (gsp:SpatialObjectCollection)
- FeatureCollection (gsp:FeatureCollection) [1]
- 871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2 Instances Co
- GeometryCollection (gsp:GeometryCollection) [1]
- LineString Instances Collection (suni:LineString_collecti

HTML result (Britannia)

Britannia

<http://www.github.com/sparqlunicorn#5853ef83-2d77-4b60-9ebd-5057c11c4422> powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin OntDoc Script 0.17

Search: Go Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL) Download Query

Property	Value
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	5853ef83-2d77-4b60-9ebd-5057c11c4422_geom (suni:5853ef83-2d77-4b60-9ebd-5057c11c4422_geom)
type (rdf:type)	871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2 (suni:871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2)
label (rdfs:label)	Britannia (xmls:string)
is member (rdfs:member) of	871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2_Instances Collection (suni:871b27c4-d62d-4a98-8578-cacc42df70d2_collection)

Metadata

Property	Value
inDataset (void:inDataset)	suni_dataset (suni:suni_dataset) [796 geocrs:longitude]

This work is released under

HTML Deployment as static OGC API Features Endpoint

The screenshot displays the QGIS interface with a map of the Hadrians Wall area. A dialog box titled "WFS-Verbindung ändern" (Change WFS Connection) is open, showing the following details:

- Name: HadriansWall
- URL: <https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/HadriansWall/index.json>
- Authentifizierung: Keine Authentifizierung
- WFS-Optionen: Version (Maximum), Objektanzahl, Objektbündelung (Voreinstellung (Serverfähigkeiten vertrauen)), Seitengröße, Achsenorientierung ignorieren (WFS 1.1/WFS 2.0), Achsenorientierung invertieren, GML2-Kodierung für Transaktionen verwenden.

The data table below the map shows the following features:

id	url
1	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/data/site/19
2	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/data/site/21
3	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/data/site/3
4	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/data/site/23
5	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/data/site/9
6	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/data/site/10
7	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/data/site/11
8	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/data/site/27
9	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/data/site/6
10	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/data/site/18

Finis!
Thx :-)

Questions?

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Timo Homburg, timo.homburg@hs-mainz.de, ORCID: 0000-0002-9499-5840

